
HOW CAN WE DEFINE ACHIEVEMENT AND SUCCESS IN HIGH PERFORMANCE TEAMS?

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Received: Dec. 2023 Accepted: Jan. 2024 Published: Feb. 2024

Abstract: Team performance is a crucial aspect of organizational success, but high performance teams (HPTs) are rare. This paper aims to determine the factors affecting successful implementation of HPTs, based on literature on teamwork, quality management, and case study literature. A model for successful HPT implementation was developed, tested through a case study organization, and an implementation program was developed to rejuvenate team performance in Australia. Communication is a key factor in team performance, but there is limited evidence on when communication becomes important. This research tested task complexity and team member diversity as facilitators of the team communication-performance relationship, and tested a team communication-performance model using established teams across two task types. The findings support the functional perspective in terms of the communication-performance relationship and help organizations understand specific types of communication activity and profiles that could offer teams a performance advantage.

Keywords: Performance, Team Management, Team Communication, Teamwork.

Introduction: It has been argued that, at least in decision-making groups, the quality of communication within the group is a major determinant of decision success (Collins & Guetzkow, 1964; Gouran & Hirokawa, 1983; Hackman & Morris, 1983). 1975; McGrath, 1984; However, despite these recommendations, there is little consideration in the literature of the impact of communication on overall team performance. Organization and Teamwork Different Ways to Measure Participation Deepening our understanding of the relationship between communication and teamwork by developing a theory using a performance perspective, Study 1 addresses several important research questions:

Although the definition of work varies in the literature, job complexity is considered an important moderating variable in the relationship between teamwork and job performance (Bowers, Pharmed, & Salas, 2000). Regarding communication and collaboration, research has shown that when teams perform complex tasks, they talk more than they do. In addition, higher cognitive needs can increase team creativity and broaden thought processes when performing complex tasks (Higgs, Plewnia, & Ploch, 2005).

This paper explores diversity, specifically gender diversity, ethnic diversity, and work value diversity, to compare variables of the relationship between team communication and performance improvement. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to increase the understanding of the impact of effective communication on employee performance. This is especially true if a company has many employees.

Understanding “work” and communication in teams is a theoretical approach that drives new research in the field to identify moderators of collaborative relationships. This allows research to determine when diversity enters into the relationship between team communication and performance.

If we can better understand the nature of team communication, including its relationship to team performance, the development of interventions to improve that communication (if needed) will become clearer. This research project contributes to the evidence base by providing new information on the relationship between team communication and performance. This research project provides literature on the methods by which communication in group work can be effective and improve group performance. In analyzing the relationship between communication and team performance, it has been

argued that the influence of team members' skills and abilities should be separated from process components such as communication.

To date, all research investigating this from a functional perspective involves groups performing decision-making tasks that define the nature of team communication and expand the business perspective by showing the type and number of tasks (or communication tasks) required for the team to perform these various tasks.

As a result of using these strategies in the workplace, the leaders of these organizations are explaining the importance of teamwork and its ability to create a better work environment for employees and increase the level of innovation, productivity and organizational success. The dynamics supporting positive engagement have been studied at the CIPD and Kingston Business School (Gourlay et al., 2012), which provided further insight into two types of work: communication and influence.

Emotional relationships are linked to employee well-being (Luth & May, 2012) and therefore lead to greater stability, are closely related to intrinsic motivation, and contribute to empowerment. Kahn (1990) has been the subject of significant participation research, and his framework describes group participation in relation to the management and distribution of individual resources to accomplish work tasks (Rich et al., 2010; May et al., 2004).

These results show that while some teams need more communication to function better, in other teams the quality of communication is more important than the quantity. More research has focused on the types of communication or interaction involved in group work (Hirokawa, 1990; Mabry & Attridge, 1990; Sundstrom, Busby, 1990), and number of researches, for example, Sorenson's found that the interactive activities of creation, production, interpretation, and evaluation based on Bales' IPA approach) were positively related to the quality of production activities.

Although these results show that different aspects of the communication process are important for different types of group work, these results do not apply to the types of secondary tasks or problem solving performed by different groups.

Sundstrom, Busby, and Bobrow (1997) sought to test the relationship between communication skills and decision-making quality in teams involved in a wilderness survival problem-solving task. The results of this study show no relationship between communication performance measures and team decision quality.

What the existing literature suggests, but does not currently demonstrate, is the context in which communication is important for team performance. A variety of theoretical approaches have been developed to explain the relationship between team communication and performance (Hirokawa & Poole, 1996) but the scope of the group's autonomy is limited. In other words, teamwork is highly structured and determined by the organization, reducing the need for collective decision-making and internal control. Most studies that have taken a functional perspective to test the relationship between communication and group decision making have used artificial or nonhistorical groups, usually three or four group members. To date, only two studies have tested the perceived performance of organizations that use periodic or permanent work teams (Graham et al., 1997; Propp & Nelson, 1996).

Similar to the general literature on team communication, studies using a performance perspective have produced consistent and mixed results regarding the importance of performance in group decision making. Hirokawa found that problem definition and solution evaluation (low quality) were the most important variables in group decision making. Replicating these activities, He also found that problem definition, solution evaluation (low quality), and criteria development were more effective and efficient for group decision making.

Extending this work, Hirokawa (1990) found that the amount of information, or the amount of important tasks involved, had a significant impact on group decision making in problem solving, classifying the solutions as i) good and ii) bad. In particular, Graham et al (1997) found significant differences between effective and ineffective decision-making groups for important tasks such as developing criteria and evaluating solutions (quality).

The above evidence suggests that problem definition is one of the most important activities in group decision making. Although these studies provide substantial (although inconclusive) evidence that specific communication styles are important for group decision making, there are few methodological weaknesses.

It has been argued that research examining the relationship between communication and group decision making should consider both functional (high performance) and non-functional (group dynamics) aspects (Salazar et al., 1994). This finding is important because it questions the validity of results examining the relationship between intrinsic strengths and group decision making and suggests the need to consider group strengths in future research examining the role of communication in group work.

Although the performance perspective has increased our understanding of the relationship between communication and group decision making, its main criticism is the inconsistency of the relationship between important tasks, performance, and decisions across courses and settings (Hirokawa & Salazar, 1999).

However, another factor that may explain differences in learning outcomes is that other factors moderate the relationship between communication and performance. Many researchers who have adopted a performance perspective have suggested that the relationship between communication and performance is influenced by moderating factors (Orlitzky & Hirokawa, 2001; Salazar, 1996). That is, we did not test whether outcome characteristics (in terms of situational and task requirements and group dimensions) were related to other differences in group decision quality.

However, the pattern of results in this study was consistent with the hypothesis that communication affects performance differently based on team characteristics and tasks. Furthermore, when information consistency and task flexibility are low, team effectiveness explains only 5% of the variance in team decision-making performance, and the significant ones (the five factors entered into the model as a block) accounted for 68 % of the variance.

When information consistency was high and task control was low, group dynamics accounted for 84% of the variance in group decision-making performance and primary motivations accounted for 6% of the variance.

Furthermore, when information coherence and performance management are low, team motivation accounts for 35% of the variance in team decision-making performance, with the most important factor contributing 30% of the variance in group decisions.

Thus, Salazar's findings, although inconclusive, suggest that there is an inverse relationship between communication and group decision-making. Specific role moderators are hypothesized to moderate the relationship between core competencies and team decision making: role structure; communication requirements; and assessment needs.

A meta-analysis found weak support for job structure as a mediator of the relationship between critical skills and decision making. However, the results supported the need for evaluation as a moderator of the effect of solution evaluation (negative consequences) on decision making.

Apart from Orlitzky and Hirokawa's (2001) meta-analytic work, which attempted to determine the predictive validity of the three job moderators proposed by Hirokawa, only two mediators of the relationship between important factors and action decisions were taken.

The existing literature explains why this paper chose to advance this area of research by examining the complexity of the work and the diversity of its members.

The group acts as a mediator in the labor relations of the communication group. Their findings provide some evidence that the general construct of task complexity moderates the relationship between team communication and performance. Effective decision making in complex work situations requires open discussion, opinions, and criticism (Fry & Slocum, 1984) this approach differs from communication in the level of interaction required.

The above results show that complex tasks can increase the cognitive processing demands of teams and improve team performance. In a study designed to test the interactive effects of task complexity and team involvement on performance, Campbell and Gingrich (1986) suggested that: Simple tasks may be less psychologically demanding on the group.

In a study of 40 employees of a large IT services organization, Campbell and Gingrich found that increased team involvement significantly improved performance on complex tasks. Flexibility of tasks Leadership and teamwork difficulties as a manager. Prior evidence from the general teamwork literature suggests that task complexity is important for managing working relationships in newsgroups.

Based on the predictive validity of the mediators tested in Orlitzky's (2001) meta-analysis of job perceptions, it can be assumed that job difficulty is important in explaining the relationship between solution evaluation and team decision making. However, based on previous findings in the general literature, it can be argued that complex tasks have a significant effect on the relationship between some important tasks and team performance, but group tasks and all important activities.

Katzenbach (1998) developed this argument from the perspective of organizational structure, suggesting that the difference between true teamwork and single-leader work teams is the quality of the decision-making process (authorization, independent of authority, decision-making local decisions). These studies suggest that work relationships occur at the individual, group, and organizational levels and that trusting relationships can mediate HPW. The research literature suggests that task complexity and team member diversity are significant mediators of the relationship between communication and team performance.

The above paragraph argued that team diversity and task complexity should be examined as mediators of the relationship between communication and team performance in order to better understand that communication is important for work together.

The questions that this research project seeks to answer require the use of valid, reliable, and meaningful methods to measure specific constructs (task complexity, team member diversity, critical thinking skills, or communication skills, and teamwork). Most research examining the relationship between communication and teamwork has been conducted using groups of students in structured environments.

However, the decision to conduct research using an existing control group involved logistical considerations (e.g., choosing time constraints, ways to encourage employee participation, give feedback, etc.) and could not see if the template was used. Through consultation with the client organizations that should participate in this study, it was decided that the activities selected will be done as a collaboration in the team building process, with employees as part of their work.

First, we examine the extent to which task complexity and team member diversity influence the relationship between communication and team performance in task-oriented teams decision. Groups within organizations perform a variety of information technology-related activities, including product and software development, technical support services, and sales and marketing, to achieve a variety of products.

For the purposes of this research project, gender diversity and ethnic diversity were identified as moderators of the relationship between communication and team performance. For this research project, the significant increase in flexibility associated with the interaction term indicated that communication activities vary with the values of task complexity and the diversity of team members (facilitators).

Based on the results, this suggests that examining the team member's perspective is more important than task-based questions such as measuring team effectiveness. The purpose of this study was to explore the extent to which job diversity and team member diversity mediate the relationship between team communication and decision making.

Regarding the relationship between team strength measures for the subarctic survival task (before discussing the team's needs) and the communication between the two tasks, a small positive correlation was found with the critical communication link for subarctic life. The difference in performance values for subarctic problem-solving communication ($r = 0.14, p < 0.05$), standard-comparison communication ($r = 0.20, p < 0.05$), and the F1 standard decision group is small, and the relationship is significant ($r = 0.15, p < 0.05$).

However, the findings show that of all the tasks required, only solution development communication has a greater impact on performance, and this occurs when the task is of low complexity. For the groups in this study, performance in decision-making improved significantly when they engaged in solution development discussions, but only when the task was simple.

Contrary to expectations, team performance under conditions of high task complexity was not influenced by the amount of communication. Additionally, in situations where evaluation is highly demanded, solution evaluation is more often discussed in the group's decision-making process.

Salazar's work is consistent with these findings and suggests that communication is more important for group decision-making under conditions that require more evaluation. However, the pattern of findings supports the hypothesis that under conditions that require more evaluation, there is more communication (without the need for action) about group decisions.

Therefore, why the groups in this study improved their decision-making performance under conditions of low task complexity remains unclear. Of course, no matter how many discussions a team has about solution development, the decision process remains the same. In addition, due to increased productivity, the number of parties involved in solution development discussions can be better determined.

However, the group shows that increasing the number of solution development options is not enough to solve the problem of sustainable decision-making. In this study, team members did not rely on solution development discussions to produce a correct response to the problem. This is an important finding because this study was specifically designed to determine whether the moderating effect of task complexity can be generalized from decision-making to production tasks.

All activities, whether decision-making, brainstorming, or production, require team members to communicate to complete tasks, solve problems, or generate ideas. Therefore, there is a positive and strong relationship between communication and team decision-making under conditions of task complexity in manufacturing. The fact that no such relationship was found suggests that task

complexity is a significant moderator of team interaction relationships only for certain types of tasks (e.g., decision making).

The primary and unique contribution of this study is the examination of team member differences as moderators of team communication relationships. As team members become more diverse, problem definition, solution development, and solution evaluation discussions must become more robust and relevant. However, group member diversity did not moderate the relationship between decision making and communication and team performance.

First, it can be seen that problem-solving communication has a greater impact on performance when there is more ethnic diversity and work value diversity in decision-making. Second, we found that solution development communication had a stronger influence on performance related to job value differences in decision-making and gender differences in performance production.

This study shows that many variables influence the relationship between team communication and performance. More importantly, these findings show that diversity moderates the relationship between certain types of communication and performance, and that this effect varies across job types. For the groups in this study, racial diversity and work value diversity were the only moderators of decision making.

These results indicate that team members' different cultural values and their work values help bring different knowledge, skills, abilities and perspectives to the team's decision-making environment. Previous studies on gender differences show that men perform better in the "utility" category activities (example like participating in the F1 Team Challenge), but women view 'marketing' as a different role (Myaskovsky, Unikel, & Dew, 2005).

In a parallel case, the information-action relationship between problem definition and solution development does not vary across decision-making and production processes. These findings suggest that these two roles are important to team performance in both types of tasks. These findings provide some support from a practical perspective to previous research that consistently finds that problem-solving communication is related to group decision-making (Graham et al., 1997; Propp and Nelson, 1996).

Several previous studies examining performance perception found that solution assessment (but not solution development discussion) was related to team decision making (Graham et al., 1997). These results indicate that the skills and abilities of team members contribute significantly to differences in team performance in decision-making.

These surprising results indicate that the skills and abilities of team members have little or no effect on team performance, but that the number of people in the team can make a difference. It is difficult to understand how the skills and abilities of the team members will have little or no significant impact on the performance of the production process. The main effects for each regression model revealed additional unexpected findings regarding the relationship between team communication and performance.

These findings indicate that teams that are more able to share solution development ideas perform better in the decision-making process. However, the amount of variance associated with this step in the regression model is only 3.9%, indicating that the integration of required tasks, the complexity of the task, and the amount of differences among team members improved the prediction of team decisions less.

However, for the production process, formulation, problem definition, solution development, and solution evaluation communication are significant predictors of team performance. Previous research

(Hirokawa, 1985, 1988, 1990) has focused more on communication processes and less on the role of groups in decision making.

Finally, the inclusion of the interaction term in the regression model significantly improved the prediction of team performance and explained an additional 10% of the variance. The results of this study confirm findings in the existing literature but also suggest that, for these groups, solution development communication is more closely related to team performance than communication. review solutions. Importantly, this study also shows that the performance perspective is a useful framework for explaining the relationship between communication and team performance in decision-making and production processes.

Although the regression models of decision-making processes show significant differences in group performance, they also show other differences (albeit important) related to the interactions of the groups and inter-group communications. A role-based approach to group communication literature has played an important role in identifying specific types of communication or core activities that are relevant to group decision-making, and recently attempted to explore the trends and changes in variables that influence group communication activities.

This research shows that although communication is important for teams to achieve high levels of performance, it affects the complexity of the tasks performed by the team. This research also shows that the composition of gender, race, and work values in a team influences the importance of communication in team performance.

This study shows that, similar to research using ad hoc groups, the inclusion of problem-solving information in group work is important. Propp et al (1996) also found that problem-solving communication was significantly related to team performance in a study using contemporary teams. However, contrary to existing findings in the literature, we found that solution development communication is more important for team performance in established teams.

A further development of this research is the use of various group activities to test performance perspectives. In fact, because of the diversity of group work, communication is more important in decision making. This article cannot determine the extent to which the complexity of the tasks and the diversity of the team members reduce the impact of the decision. If it can be shown that the team will use the information not only for decision making but in various activities to achieve goals, the overall value from a performance perspective will be greatly increased.

In other words, there are different types of work (decision, thinking, etc.) to determine the amount of information to be exchanged by the group to complete a task or to solve a problem.

However, in another study looking at job quality as a moderator of the relationship between team behavior and performance (Stewart & Barrick, 2000), it was hypothesized that the relationships between communication, conflict, clarity, and flexibility and team performance would be positive and significant for the conceptual component of creativity compared to the behavioral component of the process.

Although not all of the items considered correct were supported, it is interesting in this context that the types of statements made by the groups did not differ significantly in terms of work conditions and emotions as well as relationship between communication and action. However, research and development conducted by Katz and Tushman (1979) found little evidence that work style influences communication in certain groups.

No significant relationship was found between any type of communication activity and social work performance. Gruenfeld, Mannix, Williams, and Neale (1996) attempted to examine how groups (formal) and informal (ad hoc) groups communicate and discuss information during the decision-

making process. The results of this study show that when teams have experience working together in an organizational setting, they will be more comfortable carrying out those tasks.

At the beginning of the communication process, each group is very busy in this discussion, and most of the time is spent explaining the nature of the work or the problem of the group and the reasons, effects, and signs of action. The number of problem solving and information development activities in the fourth group is less than the most important activities in the first, second and third groups.

This study tries to address the stability found in communication activities (defined in this study) by examining the importance of work and groups in explaining the differences in communication skills. Based on the results and a review of the literature on group behavior in organizational settings, group characteristics should better explain differences in group communication performance than workplace.

Research has shown that some primary tasks (e.g., abstraction, problem solving, solution development) are stronger than others, and that the communicative function of these primary tasks differs significantly from other primary tasks. (eg, standard setting, drug review). This finding is inconsistent with the findings of Hirokawa (1988) who suggested that problem definition and problem development explain significant differences in group decision making. The reason for this surprising finding is that this study focuses on standard groups and measures the functional importance of various tasks.

Another explanation for the differences in findings, particularly regarding the discussion of developmental issues, is the nature of the working groups in the studies. Therefore, although this study did not find that communication about development standards is as important to individual performance as previous studies, these findings can support the nature of this research.

Although the findings regarding the basic function of the task are not consistent, the fact that the framework explains significant differences in communication activities across situations suggests that it is a good way to clarify group messages. Research findings using the following criteria show that problem definition is an important way to communicate with groups, both informally and formally.

However, this study found that although the requirements were different, the information groups were similar for each task. In this research, these critical tasks account for 50% of team communication. The main contribution of this study is to examine the relationship between communication messages and team performance.

There were significant differences in performance between the information groups on the production task but not on the decision-making task. In fact, better problem solving, team management and clarification, and better communication between key groups show that these important tasks are necessary for the production process. In addition, group communication or communication strategies and their relationship to group work are the focus of research of these two research projects.

Given the known difficulties in determining statistical significance, the limited number of test results found in this study reflect differences in the difficulty of the tasks and the group members involved. to group communication work relationships.

This study provides several important conclusions about the relationship between communication and team performance. We know that problem-solving communication is important, and discussing the nature of a team problem and its causes and consequences is critical to solving and building teamwork.

This study not only shows the importance of these two types of communication in group work, but also demonstrates that problem definition and communication development are very important in the discussions of the group under certain conditions as correlation analysis was used to examine the relationship between physical group building activities and desktop group communication activities.

In summary, the results obtained from this study help to explain the complex relationship between communication and team performance, showing that it depends on the complexity of the task and the diversity of the team members.

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